

21GRD07 PlasticTrace

Deliverable 4: Guidance on data library, data treatment algorithms and correlation analysis for automatic classification and recognition tools for SMPs (100-10 μ m) in complex food and environmental matrices.

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1 Executive Summary

In this document we report the realisation of usable libraries containing microplastics characteristics (e.g. FTIR and Raman spectra, decomposition product markers, physical characteristics etc.) to be further used as a support tool for microplastics identification. Moreover, is meant to provide validated strategies of data analysis and utilization for reliable identification and counting microplastics particles in a representative sample, including the comparison of different automatic recognition methods. Recognition algorithms based on correlation coefficients will be applied for specific polymer type identification.

The materials analysed are providing for different work packages in the Project.

PET microparticles with broad size distribution are available as reference material at Federal institute of material research and testing (BAM, Berlin, Germany).

2 Introduction

This report describes the data treatment and harmonisation of measurements in PlasticTrace.

Although substantial research has addressed the prevalence of plastic waste, its long-term effects on ecosystems and human health remain incompletely understood, largely due to the heterogeneous nature and complex consequences of plastic pollution. Plastic debris is typically categorized by size into macroplastics (>25 mm), mesoplastics (5–25 mm), microplastics (1 μm –5 mm), and nanoplastics (<1 μm).

There is still a lack of harmonized protocols for monitoring plastic contamination in food products and environmental matrices. Moreover, methodological advancements are needed to improve the performance assessment and uncertainty quantification of these monitoring approaches.

In the analysis of food and environmental samples, accurate identification of plastic particles is a prerequisite before quantifying and characterizing them. Micro-FTIR and micro-Raman spectroscopy are the most employed techniques for this purpose, enabling the identification of polymer types prior to measuring particle size and morphology. Identification can be performed manually—requiring trained analysts and significant time—or automatically, which allows for faster throughput and minimal operator intervention. Given the potentially high particle load in some samples, automated identification is typically recommended.

3 Objectives

First objective is the development of a comprehensive spectral data library for SMPs.

Establish an open-access, structured spectral library of synthetic microplastic particles (SMPs), including pristine particles of varying sizes and compositions, and SMPs derived from food and environmental matrices. The library will document spectral variability due to polymer composition (e.g., additives) and environmental weathering, and will be publicly available via the project website and repositories such as Zenodo.

Second objective is to design correlation-based algorithms for SMP identification. Design, develop, and validate advanced algorithms to quantify spectral correlations between unknown particles and reference data from the spectral library. The algorithms will include optimized correlation coefficients that emphasize key spectral features and define correlation thresholds to ensure identification sensitivity (true positive rate $\geq 95\%$) and quantify false positive rates. Identification uncertainty will be expressed using likelihood ratios.

4 Strategy/Methodology

This report moves the state-of-the-art on microplastic identification, developed for FT-IR spectroscopy, further by using micro-Raman spectra for particle identification while setting identification criteria applicable to spectra collected in different equipment and instrumental conditions. Compared with the wider micro-FTIR spectral band, the high selectivity of narrow peaks from micro-Raman spectra benefits identifications. The quality of spectra is quantified by a developed signal-to-noise ratio algorithm, allowing the same platform to assess spectra from different absolute intensities. It assessed the identification of PET particles whose spectra were collected in three spectrometers from three laboratories.

5 Results

This chapter describes the material and equipment used for characterisation of SMP's and the analytical procedures in different laboratories.

5.1 Fraunhofer CSP Laboratory

The laboratory at **Fraunhofer CSP** utilised a triple 557 TriVista spectrometer (S&I Spectroscopy and Imaging GmbH, Germany) equipped with a 1500 g/mm grating. A DDS laser was operated at 514 nm, with an output power of 100 mW and was focused with a $\times 50/0.75$ microscope objective. For higher resolution, a Labram Evolution HR spectrometer (Horiba) equipped with a 1800 l/mm grating was utilised. The respective laser was operated at 532 nm and focused with a $\times 50/0.75$ microscope objective. All the spectra were collected in a nitrogen-cooled 1024×256 Si-CCD camera.

Sample preparation was performed by filtering onto silicon (Si) membrane filters, following the standard operating procedure (SOP) detailed in Deliverable 1.1. Raman spectra were acquired over a shift interval of 850 cm^{-1} to 3200 cm^{-1} . Integration times varied between 1 and 10 seconds per accumulation, with 5 to 10 accumulations per spectrum. All acquisition parameters were optimized based on the specific polymer type and its physical properties to ensure spectral quality and accurate identification.

5.2 INRiM Laboratory

The laboratory at **INRiM** utilised a confocal μ -Raman HORIBA LabRAM Odyssey spectrometer equipped with a cooled (Si-CCD) detector and a 600 grooves per millimetre grating. The excitation laser had a wavelength of 633 nm, with an output power at the sample of 15 mW, and was focused with a $10\times$ objective (Olympus, NA = 0.25).

5.3 University of Parma Laboratory

The laboratory at **University of Parma** utilised a Horiba LabRAM HR Evolution (Horiba) spectrometer equipped with a liquid-nitrogen CCD detector and 600 g/mm grating. The laser was operated at 532 nm, with an output of 50 mW, and was focused with a $50\times$ Long Working Distance (LWD) magnification objective.

The spectra were collected for a Raman shift range between 415 cm^{-1} and 2060 cm^{-1} . The integration time ranged from 1 to 5 seconds per accumulation and 3 to 20 accumulations. All the Raman acquisition parameters were optimised according to the specific polymer type and its physical characteristics.

5.4 Data Acquisition and Data Treatment

For robust data harmonization in Raman spectroscopic analysis of SMPs, it is critical to account for the spectral characteristics of the filter substrates. When using silicon (Si) filter membranes, care must be taken to avoid spectral interference from the intrinsic Raman bands of Si, which appear prominently at 520.7 cm^{-1} (first order) and around 850 cm^{-1} (second order). Therefore, measurements

should be conducted in the spectral interval of $850\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to minimize substrate-induced artifacts. Additionally, as most SMPs exhibit no significant Raman features in the region between $1900\text{--}2500\text{ cm}^{-1}$, acquisition time can be optimized by focusing on the $1050\text{--}1900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range without loss of relevant chemical information. For consistent and comparable spectral data across samples, it is essential that all spectra contain the same number of data points within the selected range. It is recommended to acquire spectra using either 512 data points (yielding a spectral resolution of approximately 1.7 cm^{-1}) or 1024 points (0.8 cm^{-1} resolution), depending on the desired analytical precision. When alternative filter types—such as Anodisc, quartz, etc. membranes—are employed, the spectral acquisition range can be extended into lower wavenumber regions. However, to ensure data comparability, the spectral resolution should remain consistent with that used for Si filters. Notably, such extensions do not compromise the integrity of the chemical information in the spectra. Normalization of Raman spectra is a critical preprocessing step in data engineering to ensure that the resulting analyses reflect true chemical differences rather than artifacts from measurement conditions. Raw Raman spectra often vary in intensity due to non-chemical factors such as laser power fluctuations, sample focus, integration time, or surface morphology. These variations can obscure meaningful comparisons between spectra or lead to misleading results in multivariate statistical analyses such as principal component analysis (PCA), clustering, or machine learning classification. Normalization adjusts the spectra to a common scale, thereby enabling consistent comparison across different samples or batches. Common normalization methods include vector normalization, area normalization, and normalization to a specific reference peak (e.g., an internal standard). By removing amplitude-based variability, normalization enhances the robustness of feature extraction, improves model accuracy, and allows for reliable pattern recognition based solely on the relative spectral shape and peak positions, which are directly related to molecular structure.

In the context of SMP analysis, where subtle spectral differences may distinguish polymer types, normalization is essential to ensure reproducibility and interpretability in both qualitative identification and quantitative assessments. In Figure 1 an example of normalized PET spectra using vector normalization, in the interval $850\text{--}1900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is presented.

Figure 1. Example of normalized PET spectra using vector normalisation

While normalization is essential for reducing variability in Raman spectral data, it can introduce challenges in cases where particle size distribution is broad and automated focusing is not employed during measurement. In Raman spectroscopy, signal intensity is highly sensitive to the focal alignment between the laser and the sample surface. When particles vary significantly in size, especially in the micrometer range as is common with SMPs, smaller particles or those that are slightly out of focus may produce significantly weaker Raman signals.

Without autofocus or manual refocusing, some particles may be measured off the optimal focal plane, leading to reduced signal intensity or even signals that approach or fall below the noise level. In such cases, normalization procedures, particularly those based on total intensity or vector normalization, may amplify background noise or baseline fluctuations, inadvertently masking weak but chemically meaningful signals. This is particularly problematic in automated or high-throughput data acquisition workflows, where individual inspection of spectra is impractical.

As a result, identification becomes more difficult—not necessarily impossible—but the risk of misclassification increases, particularly for low-intensity features that may be critical for distinguishing between similar polymer types. To mitigate this, careful preprocessing strategies should be combined with consistent focusing protocols, or quality filters should be applied to exclude spectra with insufficient signal-to-noise ratios before normalization and analysis.

5.5 Method validation strategy

The validation of the identification method for polyethylene terephthalate (PET) microparticles using micro-Raman spectroscopy involved acquiring spectra from both PET and non-PET particles. Identifications were performed using the three Raman spectrometers and following the spectral acquisition protocol outlined in the previous section.

A list of the characteristic peaks of PET are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Raman shift (cm^{-1}) and peak assignment of polyethylene terephthalate (PET)

Raman shift, $\Delta\nu$ / (cm^{-1})	Assignment
3080	Aromatic C–H bonds
2960	Methylene groups adjacent to oxygen atoms
2895	C–H bond of methylene sequences
1726	Stretching C=O vibration
1615	Ring mode 8a (in Wilson's notation)
1290	C(O)–O stretching
1178	Ring in plane C–H bond and C–C stretch
1116	Ester C(O)–O and ethylene glycol C–C bonds

Manual identification of particles was conducted by evaluating the presence of at least three characteristic Raman peaks of PET at 1615 cm^{-1} , 1120 cm^{-1} , and 1000 cm^{-1} . For spectral comparisons, the Raman shift range was restricted to $852\text{--}1786\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to focus on diagnostically relevant features.

All collected spectra are provided in Supplementary Material 01 and labeled using the code format “A B (C),” where:

- **A** indicates the polymer type (“PET”, “non-PET”, or a specific polymer acronym such as PE for polyethylene [7]),
- **B** is a sequential identifier,
- **C** (in parentheses) denotes the laboratory of origin: F (Fraunhofer-CSP), I (INRiM), or UP (University of Parma).

Spectral matching was conducted using correlation algorithms defined in Table 1. Each algorithm incorporated a specific correlation coefficient (CC), selected from the following:

- **Unweighted coefficients:** Pearson (r), Spearman (ρ), and an alternative method (CPE),
- **Weighted coefficients:** r_w , ρ_w , and CPE_w, which emphasize relevant spectral regions by assigning greater importance to key features.

A total of 81 match comparisons were evaluated, comprising 27 unweighted (9 spectra \times 3 coefficients) and 54 weighted (18 spectra \times 3 coefficients) matches. These analyses were designed to assess the discriminative capability of the selected correlation metrics for accurate PET identification across different instrumentation and particle types.

After selecting a match algorithm identified by the code presented in Table 1, including the considered correlation coefficient, CC, the match between the reference spectra (PET 01 (F)) and the spectra of all the PET or non-PET particles was determined.

Table 1. Match algorithm identification code, where CC is the studied correlation coefficients. “S” specifies the type of signal considered (I , $1/I$ and $(1-I_N)$ for original, inverse and complementary intensity after signal normalisation – numbers 1, 2 or 3 from code “S#|CC|#|#”. The “d” specifies the use of the original signal, S , or its first or second derivative ($f'(S)$ and $f''(S)$) (S|d|CC|#|#) (d = 1, 2 or 3). For weighted CC, the signal was weighed (SW equal to y for yes – Code “S|d|CC|1|#”), and the wavenumber of the Raman shift was weighted directly, $\tilde{\nu}$, (“1”) or inversely, $1/\tilde{\nu}$ (“2”) (S|d|CC|SW|RW).

Match	S	d	SW	RW	Match	S	d	SW	RW
1 1 CC 1 1	I	S	y	$\tilde{\nu}$	1 1 CC 1 2	I	S	y	$1/\tilde{\nu}$
2 1 CC 1 1	$(1/I)$	S	y	$\tilde{\nu}$	2 1 CC 1 2	$(1/I)$	S	y	$1/\tilde{\nu}$
3 1 CC 1 1	$(1-I_N)$	S	y	$\tilde{\nu}$	3 1 CC 1 2	$(1-I_N)$	S	y	$1/\tilde{\nu}$
1 2 CC 1 1	I	$f'(S)$	y	$\tilde{\nu}$	1 2 CC 1 2	I	$f'(S)$	y	$1/\tilde{\nu}$
2 2 CC 1 1	$(1/I)$	$f'(S)$	y	$\tilde{\nu}$	2 2 CC 1 2	$(1/I)$	$f'(S)$	y	$1/\tilde{\nu}$
3 2 CC 1 1	$(1-I_N)$	$f'(S)$	y	$\tilde{\nu}$	3 2 CC 1 2	$(1-I_N)$	$f'(S)$	y	$1/\tilde{\nu}$
1 3 CC 1 1	I	$f''(S)$	y	$\tilde{\nu}$	1 3 CC 1 2	I	$f''(S)$	y	$1/\tilde{\nu}$
2 3 CC 1 1	$(1/I)$	$f''(S)$	y	$\tilde{\nu}$	2 3 CC 1 2	$(1/I)$	$f''(S)$	y	$1/\tilde{\nu}$

For unweighted correlation coefficients — Pearson (r) and Spearman (ρ) — the identification performance is consistent regardless of whether the raw signal intensity (I) or the normalized inverse signal ($1-I_N$) is used. However, in the case of the unweighted CPE metric and all weighted correlation coefficients, the choice of signal type (I vs. $(1 - I_N)$) can influence performance due to intrinsic differences in how each algorithm processes spectral features.

In this analysis, positive cases refer to confirmed PET particles, while negative cases correspond to non-PET particles. The 5th percentile (P_5) of match values for positive cases was estimated using bootstrap resampling to simulate the distribution of match scores. The $P5 \gg P$ value—defined as the 5th percentile of the P_5 distribution—represents the threshold above which a spectrum is identified as PET with at least 95 % confidence (i.e., a true positive rate, TP , of ≥ 95 %). This indicates that, within the evaluated PET spectra, there is a 95 % probability that a PET particle yields a match above the $P5 \gg P$ threshold against the reference spectrum "PET 01 (F)".

To estimate the false positive rate (FP), the mean (M), standard deviation (s), and total count (n) of match values for all negative cases compared to "PET 01 (F)" were calculated. The FP was derived as the complement of the cumulative t-distribution evaluated at $(P5 \gg P - M)/s$, with $n - 1$ degrees of freedom. This value represents the probability that a non-PET particle yields a match exceeding the $P5 \gg P$ threshold and is therefore incorrectly classified as PET.

All match algorithms listed in Table 1 were evaluated using this approach. An algorithm was deemed acceptable for PET identification if it met both of the following criteria:

- **True positive rate (TP) ≥ 95 %**
- **False positive rate (FP) ≤ 5 %**

When these conditions are satisfied, the likelihood ratio (LR)—defined as $LR = TP / FP$ —must not fall below 19, ensuring high discriminatory power. An FP threshold of 5 % is considered suitable for applications involving environmental or food samples, where the high particle count and potential health implications of microplastic contamination require reliable automatic identification.

Given that particle recognition accuracy can be compromised by low signal-to-noise ratios (S/N), a dedicated algorithm was developed to quantify S/N independently of absolute peak intensity scales, which may vary across instruments and acquisition settings. This S/N evaluation method, described next section, allows the identification of spectra with insufficient signal quality. Spectra exhibiting low S/N should be flagged for manual expert review rather than subjected to automated classification.

To characterise Raman spectra regarding the spectral information clarity, the highest signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) was determined as the ratio between the most intense peak of the spectrum and the signal's noise. The intensity of the most intense peak was determined as the difference between the maximum signal and the minimum signal predicted at the wavenumber of the maximum by a regression line of minimum signals of 20 wavenumber segments with equal wavenumber ranges. The noise was quantified as the mean range between the average and minimum intensity of the same Raman shift segments of the spectra.

Figure 2. Spectra a, b and c present spectra with S/N of 15 obtained from Fraunhofer CSP, INRiM and University of Parma, respectively. The mean, minimum and base regression lines of 20 wavenumber ranges are also presented. The developed algorithm was implemented in the MS Excel file used to quantify the studied spectra's match.

Table 2 presents the best-performing match algorithms, the ones associated with lower FP , considering all collected spectra and spectra with S/N larger than 10. For r and ρ , only I and $1/I$ signals were considered because (I and $1-I_N$ produce the same results). The $P5 \gg P$ estimated by the resampling bootstrap method slightly varies with the simulation run, with impact on estimated FP and LR . It is reported the $P5 \gg P$, FP , LR and the number of positive, n_+ , and negative, n_- , cases considered. For the unweighted correlation coefficients, the SW and RW is not specified.

Table 2. Best-performing match algorithms, considering all collected spectra and spectra with S/N larger than 10. The $P5 \gg P$ is the match threshold, FP the false positive rate, LR the likelihood ratio ($LR = TP/FP$), and n_+ and n_- the number of considered PET and non-PET cases.

All spectra ($n_+ = 92$ and $n_- = 82$)				Spectra with S/N > 10 ($n_+ = 80$ and $n_- = 33$)			
Match	$P5 \gg P$	$FP / \%$	LR	Match	$P5 \gg P$	$FP / \%$	LR
3 1 C_{PE_w} 1 1	0.9386	4.46×10^{-7}	2.13×10^8	1 1 r	0.6244	4.90×10^{-7}	1.94×10^8
3 1 C_{PE_w} 1 2	0.9212	5.15×10^{-5}	1.85×10^6	3 1 C_{PE_w} 1 1	0.9664	8.09×10^{-5}	1.17×10^6
1 1 r	0.4049	0.00660	1.44×10^4	3 1 C_{PE_w} 1 2	0.9734	0.000537	1.77×10^5
1 1 C_{PE}	0.5418	0.190	501	3 1 C_{PE}	0.9325	0.282	336
1 1 ρ	0.3000	0.985	96.5	1 1 ρ	0.3471	0.507	188
3 2 C_{PE}	0.3167	1.30	73.2	1 1 C_{PE}	0.5703	0.620	153
1 2 C_{PE}	0.3167	1.30	73.2	1 2 r	0.3438	0.627	151
1 2 r	0.3166	1.32	71.9	3 2 C_{PE}	0.3089	1.33	71.2
				1 2 C_{PE}	0.3051	1.45	65.6
				1 1 r_w 1 2	0.5072	1.68	56.5
				1 1 r_w 1 1	0.4692	2.93	32.4

As expected, identification performance improves and $P5 \gg P$ raises with the S/N threshold increase. Several match algorithms allow identification with LR larger than 19, where the unweighted Pearson's correlation of original signals distinguishes better positive and negative cases when a S/N threshold of 10 is considered.

Several weighted correlation coefficients can support valid PET identifications. The weighted alternative correlation coefficient, C_{PE_w} , for complementary normalised signals ($1 - I_N$) and the studied two types of weighing are the most successful weighted algorithms (3|1| C_{PE_w} |1|1 and 3|1| C_{PE_w} |1|2).

6 Conclusions

The proposed methodology for developing a robust and transferable identification protocol for microplastics using micro-Raman spectroscopy was successfully validated for polyethylene terephthalate (PET) microparticles. This approach enables identification using reference and particle spectra acquired under varying spectrometer types and acquisition conditions. A range of match algorithms was systematically evaluated, including combinations based on the original and inverse signal, with and without spectral signal derivatization. These algorithms utilized unweighted Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients, an alternative correlation metric (C_{PE}), and their respective weighted variants. For weighted algorithms, both intensity-based and wavenumber-based weighting schemes were investigated to enhance discrimination performance. The minimum match threshold ($P5 \gg P$) for PET identification was defined as the 5th percentile of the bootstrap-estimated distribution of match scores between PET reference and PET particle spectra. The bootstrap method, which does not assume a normal distribution of match values, provides a robust estimate of this threshold. To quantify specificity, the false positive rate (FP) was estimated by applying the match algorithm to spectra of non-PET particles. The FP corresponds to the probability that a non-PET particle produces a match score exceeding the $P5 \gg P$ threshold, resulting in incorrect classification as PET. A signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) quantification algorithm was developed to ensure spectral quality across instruments. Spectra with S/N values below 10 were excluded from automated identification due to insufficient signal reliability. Among the tested algorithms, the unweighted Pearson correlation coefficient applied to the original signal exhibited the best performance. Using a match threshold ($P5 \gg P$) of 0.6244, the method achieved a true positive rate of 95% with an exceptionally low false positive rate of $4.90 \times 10^{-7} \%$, indicating extremely high specificity. To support reproducibility and facilitate adoption, user-friendly spreadsheets for calculating $P5 \gg P$ and performing subsequent particle identification are provided as supplementary material.

Although promising, the developed methodology should be tested other types of SMP's like polypropylene or polyethylene as well as on aged PET particles, particles contaminated with biofilm and spectrometers.

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7 Annex